

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS ON ANIMATION BASED APPROACH

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Abstract. *In this article will be discussed, the process of enhancing listening skills, which is the basis of today's globalization and information technologies, its implementation, and the fact that the young generation has to develop their listening skill in the process of language learning.*

Keywords: *Listening skills, Animation-based learning, language learning, effective communications, motivational videos, extracurricular activities, watching movies, transcript, vocabulary building, interactive methods, group discussions, daily life.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье будет обсуждаться процесс улучшения навыков аудирования, который является основой современной глобализации и информационных технологий, его реализация, а также тот факт, что молодое поколение должно развивать свои навыки аудирования в процессе изучения языка.*

Ключевые слова: *навыки аудирования, обучение с помощью анимации, изучение языка, эффективное общение, мотивационные видеоролики, внеклассные занятия, просмотр фильмов, стенограмма, пополнение словарного запаса, интерактивные методы, групповые дискуссии, повседневная жизнь.*

Introduction: In today's digital age, effective communication skills, particularly listening, are indispensable for success in various domains of life. However, mastering listening skills can be challenging for learners of all ages. To address this challenge, educators are exploring innovative approaches, one of which is animation-based learning. This article delves into the benefits of incorporating animation into educational practices to improve listening skills and provides practical strategies for implementation.

Unless you understand, it won't matter how good a listener you are!

Initially whole world's people try to learn new languages and with that, they want to get certificates and surely communicate with other natives. In this process, they use different ways to learn language. Based on the facts, generally, we have four skills that we need to improve, if we desire to speak as a native.

So definitely these skills are :

1. Reading
2. Writing,
3. Listening
4. Speaking.

These four skills include the main part of language, especially Listening which we are going to discuss today. People have, listen and people have heard. In one word they sound the same, but there is a huge difference. Without listening, improving other skills can be so difficult. Listening is not a thing that only needs to learn another language, it is found throughout every phase of life. Effective communication often emerges from individuals who possess strong listening skills. First of all, if people want to improve their knowledge of language, they have to enhance and learn listening. Here is the way of enhancing listening skills using animations involving various strategies, including storytelling, interactive exercises, role-playing scenarios,

vocabulary building, discussions, and games. These methods leverage animated content to engage learners and improve their ability to listen attentively and comprehend information effectively.

The success of listening comprehension depends on several factors, the most important of which are individual age characteristics of the listener, speed of perception, and conditions (speed, amount and size of information, supports of perception). Listening comprehension is closely related to reading and speaking types of speech activity. Because of this, the types of speech activity have similarities and differences. These are the following: Reading, listening, and reading are receptive types of speech activity because they are aimed at receiving information. This type of speech activity is precognition and assumption. [1]

Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening is considered to be the most learned skill. Because a little more focus on learning is enhanced through simple and fun activities and ultimately leads to better results. In this case, it doesn't matter whether you work with small or large groups of students, as long as you use one of the following methods to develop yourself.[2]

1. Before start doing homework watch motivational videos in English.

It is one of the most common methods to teach and motivate learners, especially at higher educational institutes. It is so effective due to this method not only teaches students, time it encourages them at the same time.

2. Leave your comfort zone it is one of the best options If you have little time for extracurricular activities. Mostly in our daily lifestyle, we watch movies and News in our native language. That is why our ears are adapted to hear everything in our first language. However, it would be better if we start making changes to our tendencies. Begin by watching an episode of movies that you love or you interested in. Then try to watch them fully. If it is difficult to understand, replay the scene you didn't understand again and again, and also, using subtitles makes it easier.

3. Most learners think that they aren't able to understand speech especially which is in movies. But not at all, because this problem happens with almost every learner, not only with you. If you are experiencing such a problem, you can solve it by following this strategy to lose your weaknesses in listening skills. Only clean paper, a pen, and headphones are required from you. Open one of the native speaker's interviews and start to transcribe each sentence on your paper. It is such a productive manner of improving skills. It not only improves your listening but also contributes to your other skills too. If you want to get results as fast as possible, start it today!

4. Moreover if students wish to boost with their friends or with the group. We have an interactive method that is related to enhancing listening at the same time vocabulary. Choose an interesting movie, that you haven't seen before (preferably), because the plot of the film must captivate you. Of course, the film should be in a language you want to learn, and it is free to use a dictionary if you come across a word you don't know. Otherwise, the temptation to stop watching before the end of the movie is high. After watching some episodes, pause them and start to discuss what is going to happen in the following scenes. After watching a movie to the end, retell the film you watched.

In conclusion, by doing these, you are not only improving listening, meanwhile you are also improving your other abilities such as speaking, and writing. In the aftermath of these strategies, you may see how your new vocabulary has expanded. Surely all of these strategies help you understand people in the best way in your daily and work life.

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